

Barcelona as a case study for the effectiveness of short-term rental market regulations: Supplementary Materials

Annex A. Legal analysis

Table A1. The legal acts related to the short-term rental market in Barcelona

Legal act	Area of regulation or types of foreseen regulatory measures	When entered into force?	Is it still applicable?	Link
<i>Ley 5/2012, de 20 de marzo, de medidas fiscales, financieras y administrativas y de creación del Impuesto sobre las Estancias en Establecimientos Turísticos</i>	<i>taxes for stays in tourist establishments (Articles 103–114)</i>	<i>24 March 2012</i>	<i>no (repealed on 31 March 2017)</i>	https://bit.ly/3XuyCv4
<i>Ley 5/2017, de 28 de marzo, de medidas fiscales, administrativas, financieras y del sector público y de creación y regulación de los impuestos sobre grandes establecimientos comerciales, sobre estancias en establecimientos turísticos, sobre elementos radiotóxicos, sobre bebidas azucaradas envasadas y sobre emisiones de dióxido de carbono</i>	<i>taxes for stays in tourist establishments (Article 26)</i>	<i>31 March 2017</i>	<i>no (repealed on 30 April 2020)</i>	https://bit.ly/3w2nUOO
<i>Ley 5/2020, de 29 de abril, de medidas fiscales, financieras, administrativas y del sector público y de creación del impuesto sobre las instalaciones que inciden en el medio ambiente</i>	<i>taxes for stays in tourist establishments (Article 5, Article 169)</i>	<i>1 May 2020</i>	<i>yes</i>	https://bit.ly/3WaIgCf
<i>Decreto 129/2012 de 9 de octubre, por el que se aprueba el Reglamento del impuesto sobre las estancias en establecimientos turísticos</i>	<i>taxes for stays in tourist establishments</i>	<i>1 November 2012</i> <i>(revisions entered into force on 31 March 2017 and on 16 June 2017)</i>	<i>no</i>	https://bit.ly/3W9DGE7
<i>Decreto 141/2017, de 19 de septiembre, por el que se aprueba el Reglamento del impuesto sobre las estancias en establecimientos turísticos</i>	<i>taxes for stays in tourist establishments</i>	<i>22 September 2017</i>	<i>yes</i>	https://bit.ly/3WdME3g
<i>Orden VEH/216/2017, de 22 de septiembre, por la que se aprueban los modelos de autoliquidación 920, 940 y 950 del impuesto sobre las estancias en establecimientos turísticos</i>	<i>taxes for stays in tourist establishments</i>	<i>29 September 2017</i>	<i>no</i>	https://bit.ly/3QGAaAe
<i>Orden ECO/173/2021, de 31 de</i>	<i>taxes for stays in</i>	<i>1 October 2021</i>	<i>yes</i>	https://bit.ly/3

agosto, por la que se aprueban los modelos de autoliquidación 920, 940 y 950 del impuesto sobre las estancias en establecimientos turísticos	tourist establishments			H2SfoU
<i>Decreto 183/2010, de 23 de noviembre, de establecimientos de alojamiento turístico</i>	<i>requirements for professional providers</i>	<i>16 December 2010</i>	<i>no</i>	https://bit.ly/3XvzTSW
<i>Decreto 164/2010, de 9 de noviembre, de regulación de las viviendas de uso turístico</i>	<i>registration obligation</i>	<i>5 December 2010</i>	<i>no</i>	https://bit.ly/3XaxGfH
<i>Decreto 159/2012, de 20 de noviembre, de establecimientos de alojamiento turístico y de viviendas de uso turístico</i>	<i>registration obligation</i>	<i>25 December 2012 (revised: 31 March 2017)</i>	<i>no</i>	https://bit.ly/3W2O7BG
Decreto 75/2020, de 4 de agosto, de turismo de Cataluña	registration obligation	26 August 2020 (revised: 1 January 2022)	yes	https://bit.ly/3IPppom
<i>Licencing suspension in selected districts (2014)</i>	<i>licencing suspension</i>	<i>30 April 2014</i>	<i>no</i>	https://bit.ly/3Zzr4ZP
<i>Licencing suspension (2015)</i>	<i>licencing suspension</i>	<i>1 July 2015</i>	<i>no</i>	https://bit.ly/3Hc94hj
<i>Licencing suspension (2016)</i>	<i>licencing suspension</i>	<i>10 March 2016</i>	<i>no</i>	https://bit.ly/3XcflIS
<i>Pla especial urbanístic per a la regulació del habitatges d'ús turística barcelona</i>	<i>licenses limits per district</i>	<i>24 October 2014</i>	<i>no</i>	https://bit.ly/3ZwllYg and https://bit.ly/3GApzSJ
<i>Pla Especial Urbanístic per a la regulació dels establiments d'allotjament turístic (PEUAT)</i>	<i>zones and licenses (limits)</i>	<i>20 July 2017</i>	<i>no</i>	https://bit.ly/3Xeo03R
Pla especial urbanístic per a la regulació dels establiments d'allotjament turístic, albergs de joventut, habitatges d'ús turístic, llars compartides i residències col·lectives docents d'allotjament temporal	zones and licenses (limits)	26 January 2022	yes	https://bit.ly/3OFFDY4

Annex B. Datasets

Table B1. Time of data collection by Inside Airbnb – Barcelona

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
January		X	X	X	X	X	X		
February			X	X	X	X	X		
March			X		X	X	X	X	X
April	X		X	X	X	X	X		
May			X	X	X	X	X		
June			X	X	X	X	X	X	
July	X		X	X	X	X	X		
August			X	X	X	X			
September	X		X	X	X	X		X	
October	X		X	X	X	X	X		
November		X	X	X	X	X			
December		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	

Table B2. Time of data collection by Inside Airbnb – London

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
January					X	X			
February		X			X	X	X		
March			X		X	X	X	X	X
April	X			X	X	X			
May				X	X	X			
June		X			X	X	X	X	
July				X	X		X		
August				X	X	X	X		
September	X			X	X	X	X	X	
October		X		X	X	X	X		
November				X	X				
December				X	X		X	X	

Table B3. Panel data for Barcelona and London (X: observation for both cities; imputed: imputation for London data)

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
January		X (London: February)	imputed		X	X			
February			imputed		X	X	X		
March			X		X	X	X	X	X
April	X		imputed	X	X	X			
May			imputed	X	X	X			
June			imputed		X	X	X	X	
July	imputed		imputed	X	X		X		
August				X	X	X			
September	X			X	X	X		X	
October	imputed			X	X	X	X		
November		X (London: October)		X	X				
December		imputed		X	X			X	

Data restrictions

The used datasets include some limits that should be discussed. First, it is a challenging task to identify properties that are listed on Airbnb, however, are not rented on the short-term rental market anymore. Homes listed on Airbnb are often also made available via other platforms, hence such properties may be still active. In this study, all offers scraped by Inside Airbnb were included, independently from the number of reviews or dates available.

In order to examine the evolution of Airbnb supply in the various zones, the Airbnb listings were matched with the PEUAT zones. This also proved to be a challenging task, as the data extracted from Airbnb listings does not contain the precise address and location of a listing. Instead, it comprises a geographical coordinate that is randomly selected within a circle of 150 metres around the true location (Wachsmuth & Weisler, 2018). Furthermore, the coordinates in question are subject to change over time, which presents a challenge in the allocation of listings in close proximity to the boundaries of zones. In order to address these issues, each

observation of a unique Airbnb listing is paired with the zones, and the final allocation is based on the number of matches over time.

Some limitations are related to the license registry. While the overall number of licenses has been fixed in 2014, there were some updates in the registry over time. The City of Barcelona has been providing quarterly updates to the database since 2018,ⁱ however, data on license numbers is only available since 2020. As the number of entries has been stable over time (ranging from 9,502 in 2020 and 9,363 in 2023), we used the licenses from August 2023 in the paper.

Finally, some limitations are related to the control time series of Airbnb in London. The time of scraping conducted by Inside Airbnb frequently differed between the two cities, making the number of months with data available for both cities relatively low (included in the online appendix). In order to increase the number of observations in the pre-intervention training dataset, the London time series was harmonized with the Barcelona observations. Most adjustments were prepared using imputation, where missing values between dates were estimated using linear interpolation.

Annex C. Professionalisation

Figure C1. The number of single listings (listings managed by hosts with one listing)

Figure C2. The number of multi listings (listings managed by hosts with multiple listings)

The results suggest an overall decrease in small-scale service providers following the data-sharing agreement, with a small share of STR supply moved to long and mid-term rental. On the other hand, the STR supply provided by professional hosts and agencies has been relatively

stable, with an increase in longer rentals. Therefore, a higher share of non-professional hosts seems to have left the market, while the overall role of professional STR supply increased.

In order to gain further insights, we explored the professionalization of STR in the fieldwork. In Barcelona, an STR title is linked to the property and this title can be alienated together with the property. The local authority provided us a dataset with the number of transactions with properties having a STR title between 2016 and 2023, including information whether the owner is a natural or legal person. According to this dataset, there have been 3,188 transactions, that is, investors buying properties with a STR title. These transactions affected 2,735 properties, as some properties changed ownership several times. Furthermore, the dataset indicates that in 2016 individual owners represented 48%, while legal persons (that is, companies) constituted 52%. However, in 2023 these figures changed to 45% (individual owners) and 55% (legal person). From this, we can interpret that individual owners have been selling STR properties to corporate counterparts. This is expected, as STR licenses were halted in 2014 and the existing offers became very profitable with high occupancy rates. Due to profitability, STRs are an attractive product for real estate investors.

It is important to note that there are many factors besides regulatory stringency influencing professionalization. It is well known in the literature that property managers obtain higher revenues per property than amateur individual owners; and that for single listing hosts is increasingly difficult to compete with them, meaning that there is a progressive outsourcing of management. This outsourcing of management is a global phenomenon, independent of the type of the adopted regulation.

Annex F. Counterfactual analysis

Figure F1. Airbnb STR supply in London

Table F1. Pearson Correlation between Barcelona and London for Airbnb STR attributes in various time periods

	Pre-intervention (04.2015 - 07.2017)	P-val	Intervention-Covid (08.2017 - 02.2020)	P-val	Covid (03.2020 - 06.2021)	p-val	Post-Covid (07.2021-03.2023)	p-val
All Listings	0.95	0.0	-0.14	0.54	0.72	0.02	-0.16	0.71
Entire homes	0.90	0.0	-0.31	0.16	0.67	0.04	0.76	0.03
Private/shared rooms	0.96	0.0	0.14	0.53	0.67	0.03	0.68	0.07
Single-listings	0.96	0.0	-0.4	0.06	0.61	0.06	0.29	0.48
Multi-listings	0.93	0.0	0.35	0.11	0.76	0.01	0.03	0.94

Figure F2: The number of STR single-listings: Causal Impact Analysis

Figure F3: The number of STR multi-listings: Causal Impact Analysis

Table F4. Posterior Inference for Causal Impact

All STR listings

	Average	Cumulative
<i>Actual</i>	15458	618316
<i>Prediction (sd)</i>	20113 (540)	804513 (21586)
<i>95% CI</i>	[19109, 21182]	[764365, 847295]
<i>Absolute effect (sd)</i>	-4655 (540)	-186197 (21586)
<i>95% CI</i>	[-5724, -3651]	[-228979, -146049]
<i>Relative effect (sd)</i>	-23% (2.1%)	-23% (2.1%)
<i>95% CI</i>	[-27%, -19%]	[-27%, -19%]

Posterior tail-area probability p: 0.00107

Posterior prob. of a causal effect: 99.89259%

STR Entire homes

	Average	Cumulative
<i>Actual</i>	6678	267108
<i>Prediction (sd)</i>	9563 (195)	382534 (7785)
<i>95% CI</i>	[9186, 9949]	[367444, 397956]
<i>Absolute effect (sd)</i>	-2886 (195)	-115426 (7785)
<i>95% CI</i>	[-3271, -2508]	[-130848, -100336]
<i>Relative effect (sd)</i>	-30% (1.4%)	-30% (1.4%)
<i>95% CI</i>	[-33%, -27%]	[-33%, -27%]

Posterior tail-area probability p: 0.00107

Posterior prob. of a causal effect: 99.89305%

STR Private/shared rooms

	Average	Cumulative
<i>Actual</i>	8780	351208
<i>Prediction (sd)</i>	10067 (322)	402671 (12883)
<i>95% CI</i>	[9462, 10707]	[378492, 428268]
<i>Absolute effect (sd)</i>	-1287 (322)	-51463 (12883)
<i>95% CI</i>	[-1926, -682]	[-77060, -27284]
<i>Relative effect (sd)</i>	-13% (2.8%)	-13% (2.8%)
<i>95% CI</i>	[-18%, -7.2%]	[-18%, -7.2%]

Posterior tail-area probability p: 0.00108

Posterior prob. of a causal effect: 99.89247%

Single-listings

	Average	Cumulative
<i>Actual</i>	5956	238232
<i>Prediction (sd)</i>	8543 (234)	341726 (9362)
<i>95% CI</i>	[8073, 8991]	[322932, 359651]
<i>Absolute effect (sd)</i>	-2587 (234)	-103494 (9362)
<i>95% CI</i>	[-3035, -2117]	[-121419, -84700]
<i>Relative effect (sd)</i>	-30% (1.9%)	-30% (1.9%)
<i>95% CI</i>	[-34%, -26%]	[-34%, -26%]

Posterior tail-area probability p: 0.00108

Posterior prob. of a causal effect: 99.89224%

Multi-listings

	Average	Cumulative
<i>Actual</i>	9502	380084
<i>Prediction (sd)</i>	11676 (333)	467057 (13304)
<i>95% CI</i>	[11043, 12344]	[441706, 493774]
<i>Absolute effect (sd)</i>	-2174 (333)	-86973 (13304)
<i>95% CI</i>	[-2842, -1541]	[-113690, -61622]
<i>Relative effect (sd)</i>	-19% (2.3%)	-19% (2.3%)
<i>95% CI</i>	[-23%, -14%]	[-23%, -14%]

Posterior tail-area probability p: 0.00107

Posterior prob. of a causal effect: 99.89259%

ⁱ See <https://opendata-ajuntament.barcelona.cat/data/en/dataset/habitatges-us-turistic> (accessed 26 February 2024).